

REVIEWER ASSESSMENT FORM
International Conference on Responsible Tourism and Hospitality
(ICRTH) 2023

Title of Paper : Tour Guide Performance Model in Borobudur

1. Relevancy to Conference Theme: *Reviving Tourism through Green Investment AND/OR Sustaining Tourism through Cultural Heritage Conservation*

- Very relevant
 Fairly relevant
 Not relevant

- Does the abstract meet the scope of the IOP Proceeding Earth and Environmental System? **Yes/No (See list of Subjects of IOP EES under Reviewer Guidelines)**

2. Suggestions For Improving Relevancy

a) **Abstract**

The authors need to write down and emphasize the importance of the study as the background of the story. Why do they feel the need to explore this topic? Moreover, the authors need to strengthen the link of this study with the proceedings' theme and show it as one of the topics discussed in the Discussion section.

b) **Introduction:**

- The authors need to present a clearer gap of why this study is important. Furthermore, this study needs to be linked with the proceedings theme, especially in the field of cultural heritage conservation.
- No need to write the research question in the Introduction section as if it's a student's thesis. Present it as a problem statement that needs to be studied.

c) **Literature Review**

- There is a need to present past studies that display the relationship between tour guide competencies and how it significantly helps to the cultural heritage conservation.

d) **Methods and Analysis:**

- Is the description of methods adequate for replication by others (if not a standard method)?

Need to present the justification of using Atlat I version 8.

e) **Results and Discussion:**

- Are all the tables and figures self-explanatory and necessary?
- Is the discussion adequate?

Currently no discussion is provided in this section. The authors need to provide discussions of the results and support them with current references. Also, link the discussion to the theme of the conference, that is to preserve cultural heritage. The discussion helps the reader to understand more about the findings of your research.

f) **Conclusion:**

- Are there any important publications on the topic that the authors have missed? -
- Are there any evident errors? -

3. **Originality** - *Too often people simply redo work that has been done elsewhere, at times because they are not aware of previous work. Please comment on the scientific originality and usefulness of the paper.*

This reads fine.

4. **Clarity/Quality of English** – *Paper needs to be well organized and well written so that reader can understand them because of the way in which they are presented.*

The manuscript needs a good English editing.

5. **References** - *Papers show their value and their originality by grounding themselves in the literature. Ensure that the paper includes references appropriate for the kind of work. Major theoretical studies should have larger reference lists. Small case studies might only need references to their theoretical underpinnings and one or two related studies*

- The authors should provide more recent references.

6. **Length of Paper** – *Please consider whether the ideas are appropriate for the length. If the paper can be shortened, can you recommend which part(s) to be deleted or shortened?*

The manuscript length is too short (6 pages). The authors can add more in-depth discussion and relate it to the cultural heritage conservation.

7. **Comment and Feedback** - *To help the authors improve their paper, please give a written feedback to the authors*

-

8. **Recommendation** - *What is your recommendation for this paper (choose one)*

- 1. ~~Acceptance~~
- 2. **Revision**
- 3. ~~Rejection~~

REVISI 1

ABSTRACT

One of **Rebuilding Tourism for the Future through Sustainable Development by the tourism human resources**. That's a tour guide. Studies on tour guides include studies that examine the issue of tour guides from the perspectives of role, origin, and structure. This is very important because having a tour guide will make it easier for tourists to get to know the tourist destinations they are visiting. This research will fill in the ecosystem of the tourism industry and also the Heritage destination through a tour guide competency development model in Borobudur area. Data collection was carried out through participatory observation and in-depth interviews with six tour guides who are members of the HPI in the Borobudur Temple area. The data were analyzed using Atlat Ti version 9. The results of this study show that a good curriculum and training will be have a good Tour Guide Performance Model In Borobudur area. The curriculum consists of implementing (1) the scope of study, (2) content standards, (3) the teaching process, and (4) the assessment process, while the training includes (1) training needs, (2) types of training, (3) trainers, and (4) evaluation.

Keywords: Tour Guide, Tour Guide Model, Heritage destination, Rebuilding Tourism

1. Introduction

The rapid development of tourism is accompanied by Rebuilding Tourism for the Future through Sustainable Development by prioritizing the development of various sectors. One of the important sectors in sustainable tourism development is human resource development. This is very influential, where humans are the subject of Sustainable Development as the main activity. One of the actors in facilitating tourist activities in the tourism product chain is the tour guide. They perform an important function of providing quality information to tourists, which in turn enhances the experience and positive impression of the destination. These job opportunities are seen in the tourism chain, ranging from transportation, communication, attractions, rental services, entertainment, and handicraft products or creative economy

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(Cetin & Yarcana, 2017). They perform an important function of providing quality information to tourists, which in turn enhances the experience and positive impression of the destination. Therefore, the development of tourism destinations and products cannot be separated from efforts to create professional human resources, one of which is a trained tour guide (Cetin & Yarcana, 2017). Competent tour guides also influence the quality of the tourist experience (Chan et al., 2015; Rátz, 2017). They are cultural mediators and intermediaries, communicators, responsible leaders, informants, instructors, and advisors who play a direct role in mediating cultural exchanges between tourists and residents (Ababneh, 2018; Alazaizeh et al., 2019; Weiler & Black, 2015).

Studies on tour guides, among others, are studies that examine the issue of tour guides in terms of role, origin, and structure. Studies on tour guides, among others, are studies that examine the issue of tour guides in terms of role, origin, and structure (E. Cohen, 1985), problems that occur in tourist guide activities (Ap & Wong, 2001), the quality of tour guide services (Teng & Tsaur, 2021), tourist guide management (Hu & Wall, 2013), and tour guide models (Al-Okaily, 2021; Teng & Tsaur, 2021; Walker & Weiler, 2017). The study reveals many dimensions of guided tours that are important for understanding the complexity of a tour guide's work and contributing to the development of the profession. By mastering the competence of a tour guide, you will be able to work professionally.

Tour guide in cultural heritage conservation, are very needed. However, there are still few studies that discuss tour guides in cultural heritage conservation. Even though tour guides in cultural heritage conservation play an important role in Rebuilding Tourism for the Future through Sustainable Development, where tourists come and get an explanation from the Tour guide in cultural heritage conservation. And this research will fill the ecosystem gap of Rebuilding Tourism for the Future through Sustainable Development through a model of developing the competence of tour guides in cultural **heritage conservation areas**. One of **cultural heritage conservation area** is Borobudur. And this research foccus on tour guide performance model in borobudur area. This model based on curriculum and training for tour guide performance.

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2. Literature review

2.1. Tour Guide

Working in tourism becomes very important when someone must be able to adapt competencies holistically between the needs and developments of the times. One of the fields of work is a tour guide. Mastery of tour guide competence is very necessary in Rebuilding Tourism for the Future through Sustainable Development so that tourists are satisfied and come back to tourist destinations. Tour guides are people who accompany tourists who are on a tourist trip, so in carrying out their performance, special skills are needed that must be learned and achieved professionally (Cetin & Yarcana, 2017). The tourism industry needs tour guides to support several functions in tourism. These functions include tour guide as communicator and role as ambassador (Aloudat, 2017; Teng & Tsaur, 2021), who are able to create good relationships with tourists (Hwang & Lee, 2019) so they must work professionally.

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Another function makes tourists revisit because of memorable experiences, especially when visiting heritage sites (Pine & Gilmore, 1998) where a guided tour of a heritage site has routes and stories recorded about heritage sites (Chelaramani et al., 2017). Effective guiding techniques are able to minimize the negative impact of tourists on heritage destinations by increasing the sustainable behavior of visitors (Rutherford et al., 2015).

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The competence of tour guides can be developed through tourism education (Sukrispiyanto & Setiawati, 2020; Yani et al., 2020) went through extensive training stages (Yoga et al., 2022) in order to acquire expertise, knowledge, and skills (Weiler & Black, 2015) towards competence. Competent tour guides are able to provide satisfaction for tourists and will make repeat visits (Chan et al., 2015).

2.2. Competency Model

Competence is a concept that is relational to a competent work situation (Wilkinson et al., 2010). Competence is a person's underlying characteristic of "how to behave or think, understand the whole situation, and endure for a long enough period of time enumerating five characteristics of competence, namely (1) motivation, (2) character, (3) concept, (4) science, and (5) skill. This competent character is able to be an indicator of appearance in a person working rationally. Competence relates to the quality of a person at work. Someone who works competently tends to be excellent achievers (Levenson et al., 2006). Competence emerged as a concept of motivation to achieve competence (White, 1959), achieve competency functions in accordance with the competence of the field of work and professionalism in work (Amage et al., 2014). Competencies will change the way a person works through job responsibilities with a focus on technical and behavioral performance. With this competency, performance appraisal clearly addresses what is being assessed and how to assess it.

The application of performance appraisal relates to what and how to assess through competence. These competencies relate to performance situations, communication skills, and service skills (Gaffard, 2007). In this case, the performance assessed is related to these skills so that in its development there are several competency models. The management-focused competency model is known as the Lancaster Managerial Competency Model as a universal or general management competency framework (Burgoyne & Stuart, 1976). Burgoyne and Stuart grouped competencies into three main groups, namely (1) the level of basic knowledge and professional knowledge relevant to competency achievement indicators, namely being able to understand knowledge of the field of performance (general knowledge, interdepartmental relations, and objectives of the field of performance); (2) skill level with indicators of competency achievement, namely skilled, resolute, able to withstand emotions, and responsiveness; (3) the level of meta-quality of self with indicators of competency achievement, namely creative, being kind, and always developing themselves. In this model, personal qualities have been contained, but they are still general as competencies that must be mastered in the company's managerial so that they can still be developed specifically for the implementation of the stages.

2.3. Tour Guide Competency Model

The tour guide competency model that has been studied is a sustainable training and transformative model (Walker & Weiler, 2017). This model focuses more on ecotourism guidance with indicators of training, personal qualities, and attitudes towards loving the environment. The competency model of tour guides is also developing according to the needs of the tourism ecosystem. This model focuses on appearance while working (Al-Okaily, 2021). Assessment orientation on tasks, constructive behavior and counterproductive attitude in tour guides.

Tour guide competency models in developing countries focus more on training tour guides with the aim of increasing sustainable capacity (Weiler & Ham, 2002).

2.3.1. Curriculum

The curriculum is closely related to how a competency is structured and taught for tour guides. Existing competencies are contained in a curriculum. In the education curriculum, there are knowledge, skills, and innovation (Wattanacharoensil, 2014) where the tourism education curriculum has a reference for the development of tourism education (Oktadiana & Chon, 2017). The development of tourism curriculum content in Indonesia consists of skills, knowledge and attitudes identified by considering their application (Yusuf et al., 2018). The application consists of (1) the scope of study, (2) content standards, (3) the teaching process and (4) the assessment process. This study specifically addresses the relationship of curriculum with the scope of study related to tour guides as the most essential. Tourism curriculum that contains skills in the field of tourism performance, one of which is to contain tour guide skills as the core curriculum (Tang & Gao, 2012). The tour guide skills curriculum as a core curriculum can provide a reference in the focus of competency development.

2.3.2. Training

Good training is part of an inseparable curriculum. To be able to achieve competence it is necessary to develop and implement a number of mechanisms, such as training, professional certification and tour guide licenses. Training is a process of knowledge transfer (Freire, 2013). This tour guide competency training can be carried out properly by implementing the references regulated in the curriculum. Training

(Wilkinson et al., 2010) is a systematically planned program, which contains four stages, namely (1) identification of training needs, (2) types of training, (3) trainers, and (4) follow-up and evaluation. These four stages need to be implemented in order to be able to improve the performance of tour guides. Training in tour guidance can improve the performance of tour guides (Ong et 'al., 2014). Training - training is necessary so that tour guides are able to work well to achieve competent capacity. Tour guide training will support their competence (Mason & Christie, 2003).

3. Methodology

This study used qualitative methods. Participatory observation and in-depth interviews were used to collect data. The in-depth interview was conducted with Data collection was carried out through participatory observation and in-depth interviews with six tour guides who are members of the HPI in the Borobudur Temple area. The data were analyzed using Atlat I version 9. Atlas/ti is analyze program for analyzing communicated messages (Ronzani et al., 2020). This section is a qualitative analysis that explains the answers to research questions after interviews with informants. The analysis step, first coding by entering curriculum and training data. Then the data is synthesized and analyzed to identify the theories and concepts learned by the researcher. The following sections will discuss each theme in depth in developing the conceptual framework of the Tour Guide Performance Model In Borobudur (Figure 1)

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4. Results and Discussions

The results of this study show that a good curriculum and training will form a model for developing tour guide modules in the Borobudur Temple area. The curriculum consists of the implementation of (1) the scope of study, (2) content standards, (3) the teaching process, and (4) the assessment process, while the training includes (1) training needs, (2) types of training, (3) trainers, and (4) evaluation.

4.1. Curriculum

(1) Scope of Study,

The curriculum implemented has used studies that are integrated with the cultural diversity curriculum so that tour guides can easily understand the material and implement it in work. The curriculum developed has been carried out continuously and planned so that it has novelty that can be adopted by tour guides. This tour guide curriculum development model is an attitude display of curriculum implementation that contains ideas, characters and processes of mastering interrelated material.

In addition to the curriculum, tour guides in the Borobudur area have implemented the Innovated service Organization and Management Model in serving tourists. This can be seen from the way they transfer information when guiding using thematic methods in the Borobudur Area. This thematic method is able to provide flexibility for tourists to enjoy the tour guide process.

(2) content standards,

The content standard contains references in learning that will be derived into subject matter by providing opportunities and structured freedom for tour guides to improve the mastery of technical competencies (hard skills) and work culture (soft skills) that apply at the Borobudur Heritage destination location. It was found that the curriculum was prepared by competent parties from the association of Indonesian tour attendant associations. In addition, in the curriculum there is also an allocation of achievement time in accordance with the tour guide scheme and contains benefits.

(3) The teaching process,

The teaching process includes mastery of knowledge of Borobudur Heritage destinations, attitudes to serve tourists, and story telling techniques using foreign languages. The teaching process includes the technical delivery of presentation material that is easy to understand with modules. This teaching module is

distributed according to the material delivered with a good teaching approach method and in accordance with the number of tour guides.

(4) assessment process,

The process of assessing the competence of tour guides in Borobudur Heritage destinations is a process of evaluating the skills, knowledge, attitudes, and behavior of tour guides in carrying out their duties.

Skill assessment consists of a tour guide competency assessment process to ensure that tour guides have adequate qualifications and can provide a safe, informative, and satisfying travel experience for tourists in Borobudur Heritage Area destinations. The assessment process is carried out through practical examinations in accordance with the material delivered with adequate assessment duration and there is a follow-up of training assessment results (competent or not yet competent)

4.2. Training

(1) Tour Guide Performance Training Needs

Tour guide training in Borobudur Heritage destinations focuses on the following skills:

- a. **Knowledge Base:** Historical, Cultural Knowledge and Local Insights especially Borobudur Heritage Destination. Tour Guide have understood as well about the history, culture, and philosophy in Borobudur Heritage Destination. And also able to explain information about history, local culture, local customs and recent developments in the area.
- b. **Quality Service:** as a good tour guide, the have to be a good Hospitality services and problem-solving. They have to know how to handle unexpected situations and solve problems in Borobudur Heritage Destination and also have a customer-centric services mindset, focusing on making the tour enjoyable and memorable for participants.
- c. **Communication Skills:** tour guide have to be a good Public Speaking, Language Skills, and Interpersonal Skills. Tour guide performance in effective public speaking techniques, including voice projection, articulation, and engaging storytelling with international tourists.
- d. **Good Navigation:** tour guide have to create and know the Route Planning and consist with interesting route, time schedule and total tourist handled. It was included by Emergency Procedures when evacuation procedures and first aid basics for tourists.
- e. **Environmental Awareness:** **tour guides need to explain about Sustainability** by teaching tourists the principles of sustainable and responsible travel by explaining the use of special sandals and special clothing when at Borobudur Heritage Destination.
- f. **Cultural Sensitivity:** training that provides understanding for guides to be sensitive to cultural differences and tourist behavior.

(2) Tour Guides Types Of Training,

Training provided for tour guides in Borobudur Heritage destinations is in the form of classroom teaching, practice and learning at work by traveling around the Borobudur Temple Area and its surroundings. This practice consists of guiding techniques in the form of introductions, guiding content and closing

(3) Tour Guide Compliance Trainers,

Training provided for tour guides in Borobudur Area Heritage destinations are guided by tour guides from the Indonesian Tourist Association, international tour guide practitioners and heritage area tour guides.

(4) Tour Guide Evaluation

This practice evaluation is in the form of the practice of guiding tours in the Borobudur heritage area with competent or incompetent results organized by the Tour Guide Professional Certification Institute and the Indonesian Tour Guide Association (HPI) Central Java.

Based on two things (Curriculum and Training), the results of the Tour Guide Performance Model In Borobudur include:

- a. Resolute and resolf of the conficts, namely When tourists experience difficulties, these tour guides provide the right solution
- b. Problem Solving Skills is the ability of tour guides to identify problems, analyze answers, and implement the best solutions.
- c. Interpersonal Skills are the ability to control themselves, have a high sense of empathy and have a good leadership spirit
- d. Innovation Skills and able to advance technology is able to adapt to technological advances
- e. Critical Thinking and decision making is being able to think intellectually in a reflective, independent, and rational manner. This includes the ability to provide interpretation, informative and argumentative in interpreting and deciding according to observations, information, and argumentation.
- f. Collaboration is the ability to work with tourists and other workers
- g. Self Confidence is having high confidence in carrying out duties as a tour guide
- h. New Ideas and Solution is to have ideas in making the guiding atmosphere happy and familiar
- i. Apply and synthesize information, namely the Borobudur tour guide has compiled the guide material well so that the tourists are clear and revisit intention

Here is the tour guide's performance model

Figure 1

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

The curriculum and the training includes (1) tour guide performance training needs, (2) tour guides types of training, (3) tour guide compliance trainers, and (4) tour guide evaluation is good. However, existing developments are added to the mastery of technological sophistication, especially how to use social media properly and correctly so that it is always connected with tourists who have been guided and tour guides provide good performance.

REVISI 2

A tour guide's performance model for sustainable heritage at Borobudur

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Abstract

Expanding the workforce in the tourism sector is a key aspect of the Rebuild Tourism for the Future via Sustainable Development initiative of which tour guides may become an essential part. Tour guide positions involve providing detailed explanations about heritage attractions and instructing tourists on acceptable behaviour during their investigation of these sites. This research is significant because tour guides play a crucial role in the preservation of tourism by safeguarding cultural treasures. Research on tour guides involves analyses that explore the subject from the viewpoints of their function, history, and structure. This study aims to enhance our understanding of the ecology of the tourism industry and heritage destinations by developing a model for the competent development of tour guides at Borobudur. Data was collected through participatory observation and in-depth interviews with six tour guides in Borobudur who are members of the Indonesian Tour Guides Association. The data were examined utilising Atlas Ti version 9. The study's findings suggest that implementing a high-quality curriculum and training programmes

could lead to an exceptional performance model for tour guides at the Borobudur. The curriculum encompasses the implementation of four key components: (1) the scope of study, (2) content standards, (3) the teaching process, and (4) the assessment process. On the other hand, the training aspect covers four elements: (1) training needs, (2) types of training, (3) trainers, and (4) evaluation.

Keywords: Tour Guide Model, Heritage Destination, Rethinking Tourism

5. Introduction

The exponential growth of tourism is complemented by the implementation of Sustainable Development in Rebuilding Tourism for the Future, with a focus on advancing many sectors. Enhancing human resources is a crucial aspect in the development of sustainable tourism. This is highly significant, as humans are the focal point of Sustainable Development as the primary undertaking. These work opportunities can be found within the tourism industry, encompassing several sectors such as transportation, communication, attractions, rental services, entertainment, and the production of handicraft products or creative economy [1]. Hence, the establishment of tourism locations and products is intrinsically linked to the endeavour of cultivating proficient personnel, such as a skilled tour guide [1]. The tour guide is a participant in the tourism product chain who promotes and facilitates tourist activities. Tour guides play a crucial role in providing guests with precise information, enhancing their experience, and fostering a favourable perception of the location. Tour guides who possess extensive expertise have a significant impact on the overall quality of the tourist experience [2,3]. They serve as cultural mediators and intermediaries, facilitating communication and acting as responsible leaders, informants, educators, and consultants. Their main duty is to mediate cultural exchanges between tourists and inhabitants [4,5,6].

Studies on tour guides focus on analysing the role, origin, and structure of tour guides [7], identifying difficulties that arise during tourist guide activities [8], evaluating the quality of tour guide services [9], exploring tourist guide management [10], and proposing several tour guide models [11, 9, 12]. The study uncovers many facets of guided tours that are crucial for comprehending the intricacy of its operations and aiding the advancement of the profession. By acquiring expertise in the field of tour guiding, individuals will be capable of performing their job with a high level of professionalism.

There is a significant demand for tour guides specialising in cultural heritage conservation. However, the investigation into the role of tour guides in safeguarding cultural assets is currently at its nascent phase. Tour guides play a crucial role in preserving cultural assets and promoting sustainable tourism by providing travellers with explanations on cultural heritage conservation. Ensuring the sustainability of the culture is of utmost importance. Tourists can gain an understanding of proper conduct in cultural heritage sites with the guidance of a tour guide. Furthermore, this project aims to address the existing gap in the ecosystem of Rebuilding Tourism for the Future Sustainable Development by implementing a model that enhances the skills and expertise of tour guides in the preservation of cultural heritage sites.

The argument acknowledges the need for incorporating environmental awareness into the tour guide curriculum, but it lacks particular illustrations of the content that should be covered in this training. To mitigate the adverse impacts of travel, the emphasis will be placed on educating visitors about environmental stewardship during their journeys. Adopting this mindset will decrease hostile behaviours

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and have a beneficial influence on society and the environment [13]. Sustainable tourism refers to the use of comprehensive systems and mindsets that promote the sustainable utilisation of resources [14]. The idea of sustainability was driven by the following key concepts: The four main areas of focus are: (1) preservation of the environment; (2) safeguarding human culture and variety; (3) promoting sustainable economic growth; and (4) implementing comprehensive development strategies [15]. Hence, the curriculum and training components necessitate a focus on environmental consciousness with the objective of enhancing sustainability. The process include instructing tour guides on ethical and environmentally sustainable tourism practices, with the aim of establishing a targeted strategy to mitigate the adverse environmental impacts of tourism. Visitors' positive experiences and satisfaction with tour guides' performances promote sustainable behaviour and reduce the negative effects on historical monuments [5].

Borobudur is one of the locations dedicated to the safeguarding of cultural heritage. Therefore, this study centres on developing a model to evaluate the effectiveness of tour guides in the Borobudur area. This strategy is founded on a curriculum and training programme designed to enhance the performance of tour guides.

6. Literature review

6.1. Tour guide

Proficiency in the hospitality industry is crucial for individuals to effectively adjust their skills to the evolving needs and trends of the industry. One area of employment is the field of information technology. Proficiency in the skills and knowledge of tour guides is crucial for the future of tourism, as it ensures that tourists are content and inclined to revisit tourist locations. This is particularly important in the context of sustainable development. Tour guides are those that accompany visitors on trips, and in order to effectively perform their duties, they must possess and acquire specialised skills in a professional manner [1]. Tour guides are essential for several responsibilities within the tourism industry. These functions encompass tour guides as both communicators and ambassadors [9, 16]. They possess the ability to establish positive rapport with tourists [17], necessitating a professional approach to their work.

Another role of tour guides is to ensure that tourists are compelled to return due to the exceptional experiences they have, particularly while seeing heritage sites [18]. These guides provide detailed instructions and descriptions of historical locations during guided tours of these significant sites [19]. Efficient guiding approaches can mitigate the adverse effects of tourists on cultural places by promoting environmentally conscious behaviours among visitors [20]. Tour guides can enhance their competence by undergoing tourist education [21,22] and engaging in rigorous training programmes [23] to obtain expertise, information, and skills [6] necessary for achieving competency. Proficient tour guides can ensure tourist satisfaction and encourage return visits [2].

6.2. Heritage tour guide

Heritage places hold importance as tourism destinations that focus on promoting cultural awareness [24]. One of the tourism complexes is included as a World Heritage Site. Due to their increasing popularity, cultural heritage tours have grown more captivating to visit. Consequently, there is an increasing influx of tourists with a wide range of ideas and personalities. The presence of many characteristics and behaviours, such as littering, vandalism, and pollution, might have a detrimental effect on the area [25]. Nevertheless, a tour guide can identify this, along with other factors, by

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monitoring the path traversed [19]. The primary role of this tour guide is to advocate for the preservation of the environment and cultural heritage, so encouraging tourists to embrace sustainable and ethical practices [26]. It is crucial to provide guidance to tourists regarding appropriate behaviour and effective exploration tactics. By implementing a sustainable tourist experience, the utilisation of interpretation by a knowledgeable guide proves to be an effective technique in reducing the detrimental impact of tourists on heritage objects [27,28]. Nevertheless, the aptitude associated with the performance of this important position still has to be determined. Despite the crucial role that tour guides play in excursions, some of them have not yet reached the pinnacle of their knowledge. Tour guides' performances have a significant direct influence on tourists' satisfaction with their services and a secondary influence on their whole tour experience [11]. It is essential to identify the suitable model of tour guide competence.

6.3. Tour guide competency model

Competence is a term that is associated with a job environment where someone is skilled and capable [29]. There are five key elements that define competence: (1) motivation, (2) character, (3) concept, (4) science, and (5) skill. This competent persona is an individual who demonstrates competence in their profession typically excels in their performance [30]. Competence is a motivational concept that drives individuals to achieve proficiency [31], and to acquire the necessary skills and expertise in their professional sector [32]. Competencies will alter an individual's approach to job duties, emphasising both technical and behavioural performance. This competency ensures that the performance appraisal process effectively identifies and evaluates the specific aspects that are being examined and provides clear guidelines on how to conduct the assessment. The application of performance appraisal pertains to the evaluation of competence and determining the methods and criteria for assessment. These qualities pertain to situations where performance is required, as well as skills in communication and providing service [33]. In this instance, the evaluation of performance is linked to these specific talents, thereby necessitating the use of various competency models in their enhancement.

The tour guide competency model that has been examined is a training strategy that promotes sustainability and transformation [17]. This model places a greater emphasis on providing direction for ecotourism, namely in terms of training, personal attributes, and attitudes towards environmental stewardship. Moreover, the tour guide competency model is adapting to fulfil the requirements of the tourism industry. This model prioritises aesthetics during operation [11]. Evaluation of task orientation, constructive behaviour, and counterproductive attitude among tour guides. The competency models for tour guides in underdeveloped countries primarily emphasise training tour guides to enhance their sustainable ability [35].

6.3.1. Curriculum. The curriculum is intricately linked to the organisation and delivery of competencies for tour guides. The programme encompasses the current competencies. The education curriculum

encompasses knowledge, skills, and innovation [36], which serve as a framework for enhancing learning in the field of tourism [37]. The selection of skills, information, and attitudes incorporated into Indonesia's tourism curriculum is based on their effectiveness [38]. The application comprises four components: (1) the study's scope, (2) content standards, (3) the teaching procedure, and (4) the assessment process. This study primarily examines the correlation between the curriculum and the extent of study pertaining to tour guides, which is considered the most crucial aspect. The tourism curriculum incorporates skills related to tourist performance, including the integration of tour guide competences within the core curriculum [39]. The inclusion of the tour guide skills curriculum as a core curriculum can serve as a valuable resource for enhancing competency development.

6.3.2. *Training.* Good training is an inseparable part of curriculum. To be able to achieve competence, multiple processes must be constructed and put on practice, such as training, professional certification and tour guide licenses. Training is a process of knowledge transfer [40]. This tour guide competency training can be carried out properly by implementing the references regulated in the curriculum. Training [29] is a systematically planned program which contains four stages (1) identification of training needs, (2) types of training, (3) trainers, and (4) follow-up and evaluation. These four stages need to be implemented in order to possess the ability for improving tour guides' performance. Tour guides' performance can be improved by training in tour guiding [41]. Tour guides need to get training for themselves to perform effectively and reach competent capacity. Tour guide training will support their competence [42].

7. Methodology

This study employed qualitative methodologies. The data was gathered through in-depth talks and interactive observation. Subsequently, a comprehensive dialogue occurred, involving six tour guides from the Borobudur region who are affiliated with the Indonesian Tour Guides Association. Informants are qualified guides who have a competence certificate, have been working for at least 5 years, and have fluency in a foreign language. The questions related to the curriculum, training, and performance based on hospitality and outstanding service. And they actively contributed to the data collection process by conducting thorough interviews and engaging in participatory observation. The data were examined via Atlas TI version 9. Atlas/Ti is a software programme designed for the analysis of conveyed messages [43]. This part comprises a qualitative analysis that elucidates the responses to research inquiries subsequent to conducting interviews with informants. The stakeholders' comprehensive explanations, actions, and observations from the interview were classified in this research. The analytical resources produced by Atlas.TITM make a valuable contribution to scientific research, particularly in the field of social sciences [43,44].

The analysis phase consists of multiple processes, commencing with the input of curriculum and training data through coding. Next, the data is processed and examined to discover the theories and concepts acquired by the researcher. The subsequent sections will provide a comprehensive analysis of each theme in order to construct the conceptual framework of the Tour Guide Performance Model in Borobudur.

4. Results and discussions

Borobudur is a renowned cultural site in Indonesia. The temples of Borobudur, including Borobudur and Mendut temples, have been officially classified as heritage sites. Heritage sites necessitate exploration under the guidance of a tour guide. The investigation conducted at Borobudur disclosed that tour guides had a track record of expertise. The stages of understanding the curriculum for the tour guide and completing the training were crucial in developing this ability.

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Provide more specific details about the methodology, such as the criteria for selecting participants, the duration of observations, and the specific questions asked during interviews.

Both of these components establish a structure for the model that this study will embrace. This concept can be utilised to revitalise tourism in the future by focusing on sustainable development, particularly in heritage destinations.

Tour guides have the necessary expertise to instruct and elucidate to tourists the appropriate conduct to be observed at the heritage site, acquired via comprehensive curriculum study and training completion. Tour guides have acquired expertise in this process of leading tours. The implemented curriculum effectively enables tour guides to understand the notion of guiding heritage through coaching provided by teachers who have competence in the business. In order to obtain professional tour guide certification, tour guides must successfully complete various sorts of tests as part of their education and training requirements. Upon achieving proficiency, individuals will receive a certificate of competence, which can be utilised to obtain their identity card.

The identification of training needs, the various types of training, the selection of trainers, and the evaluation process are all components of training. Similarly, the curriculum encompasses the area of study, content standards, the teaching technique, and the assessment process. Thus, tour guides can effectively fulfil their role by recommending that tourists wear appropriate attire, such as clothing and sandals (Upanat), when visiting Borobudur Temple with an environmentally responsible mindset. In addition, it imposes limitations on the amount of tourists allowed to visit the Borobudur temple and prohibits them from ascending the monument, littering, or defacing its walls with graffiti. The investment viewpoint of this tour guide is expected to impact the long-term viability of tourism by preserving and promoting cultural assets.

Figure 1. Borobudur Heritage Site.

4.1. Curriculum

4.1.1. Scope of study. The adopted curriculum incorporates studies that are interwoven with the cultural diversity curriculum, enabling tour guides to comprehensively grasp the content and effectively use it in their profession. The curriculum has been consistently implemented and strategically designed to incorporate innovative elements that can be utilised by tour guides. The tour guide curriculum development model is a framework that showcases the application of curriculum through the demonstration of attitudes, ideas, characters, and processes. It aims to facilitate the mastery of associated information.

Tour guides in the Borobudur area have adopted the Innovate service Organisation and Management Model to enhance their service to tourists, alongside the curriculum. This is evident in the manner in which they provide information while providing guidance employing thematic approaches in the Borobudur Area. This theme approach offers travellers the opportunity to experience the tour guide process with flexibility.

4.1.2. Content standards. The content standard contains references to learning that will be derived from subject matter by providing opportunities and structured freedom for tour guides to improve the mastery of technical competencies (hard skills) and work culture (soft skills) applied at the Borobudur (Heritage destination location). It was found that the curriculum was prepared by competent parties from the association of Indonesian tour guide associations. In addition, in the curriculum there is also an allocation of achievement time in accordance with the tour guide scheme which contains benefits.

4.1.3. *The teaching process.* The training approach encompasses the acquisition of expertise in Borobudur, the cultivation of a service-oriented mindset towards tourists, and the utilisation of foreign languages for effective storytelling. The teaching process involves the proficient delivery of presentation content that is comprehensible through the use of modules. This training module is disseminated based on the content presented with an effective teaching methodology and in alignment with the number of tour guides available.

4.1.4. *Assessment process.* The training approach encompasses the acquisition of expertise in Borobudur, the cultivation of a service-oriented mindset towards tourists, and the utilisation of foreign languages for effective storytelling. The teaching process involves the proficient delivery of presentation content that is comprehensible through the use of modules. This training module is disseminated based on the content presented with an effective teaching methodology and in alignment with the number of tour guides available.

4.2. *Training*

4.2.1. *Tour guide performance training needs.* Tour guide training in Borobudur as Heritage destinations focuses on the following skills:

- g. **Knowledge Base:** Historical, Cultural Knowledge and Local Insights especially Borobudur as Heritage Destination. Tour Guide have understood well about the history, culture, and philosophy in Borobudur and also able to explain information about history, local culture, local customs and recent developments in the area.
- h. **Quality Service:** as good tour guides, they have to have a good hospitality services and problem-solving skills. They have to know how to handle unexpected situations and solve problems at Borobudur Heritage Destination and also have a customer-centric service mindset, focusing on making the tour enjoyable and memorable for participants.
- i. **Communication Skills:** tour guides have to have a good public speaking, language skills, and interpersonal skills. Tour guide should present performances using effective public speaking techniques, including voice projection, articulation, and engaging storytelling to international tourists.
- j. **Good Navigation:** tour guide has to create and know the route planning and includes an interesting route, time schedule and total number of tourists handled. It is included in emergency procedures for evacuation procedures and first aid basics for tourists.
- k. **Environmental Awareness: tour guides need to explain** Sustainability by teaching tourists the principles of sustainable and responsible travel by explaining the use of special sandals and special clothing when at Borobudur Heritage Destination.
- l. **Cultural Sensitivity:** training that provides understanding for guides to be sensitive to cultural differences and tourist behavior.

4.2.2. *Tour guides types of training.* The training offered to tour guides at Borobudur, specifically at heritage destinations, encompasses classroom instruction, practical exercises, and on-the-job learning through exploration of the Borobudur region and its environs. This method involves employing techniques in the form of introductions, leading material, and closing.

4.2.3. *Tour Guide Compliance Trainers.* The training for tour guides in the Borobudur region is conducted by experienced tour guides from the Indonesian Tourist Association, as well as international tour guide professionals and local guides familiar with the heritage region. This is highly beneficial for the revitalization of tourism in the future, particularly for heritage areas, by promoting sustainable development.

4.2.4. *Tour guide evaluation.* This evaluation is a practical assessment of tour guiding skills in the Borobudur historic region. It is conducted by the Tour Guide Professional Certification Institute and the Indonesian Tour Guide Association of Central Java to determine the level of competence in guiding tours. The outcomes of Borobudur's Tour Guide Performance Model are determined by two factors: the curriculum and the training provided.

- j. The resolution and determination of conflicts can be achieved when tourists encounter challenges, as these tour guides offer appropriate solutions.
- k. Problem-solving skills refer to the capacity of tour guides to recognise issues, examine potential solutions, and effectively apply the most optimal course of action.
- l. Interpersonal skills refer to the capacity to regulate one's own behaviour, possess a strong sense of empathy, and exhibit effective leadership qualities.
- m. Possessing innovation skills and the ability to improve technology is essential for adapting to technological advancements.
- n. Critical thinking and decision making necessitate the ability to engage in intellectual reflection, independence, and rationality. This encompasses the capacity to offer interpretation that is both instructive and contentious, based on observations, information, and reasoning.
- o. Collaboration refers to the capacity to cooperate and engage with tourists and fellow colleagues.
- p. Self-confidence refers to the state of having a strong belief in one's ability to effectively perform the responsibilities of a tour guide.
- q. The proposed concepts and solutions aim to create a joyful and welcoming atmosphere for guidance.
- r. The Borobudur tour guides have effectively produced the guide material to ensure that tourists understand and remember their intended purpose.

Historical site research is the examination of artefacts and architectural structures to understand the evolution, origin, and context of societies. The ultimate aim is to draw historical conclusions. Tourists would have a clearer comprehension of the cultural significance of the presented history and the knowledge gained from the tour if they were accompanied by a tour guide. The tour guide enables travellers to comprehend and learn about the cultural legacy present in Borobudur. The present study was based on the performance of tour guides, which served as a demonstration of their competency as tour guides. This strategy also recognises the crucial role that the talents of qualified tour guides play in historical sites. The literature evaluation suggests that the effectiveness of tour guides at Borobudur in terms of their proficiency is influenced by the curriculum and training they get.

The literature study suggests that both curriculum and training are essential components. The establishment of favourable interactions between tour guides and tourists can be influenced by the adoption of curriculum and training programmes. Positive encounters of this nature are anticipated to enhance tourist happiness and augment their understanding of heritage places, thereby leading to an improvement in promotion through word-of-mouth. The study will then examine the long-term viability of the location by evaluating the actions of visitors and the effectiveness of tour guides at the historical site.

Figure 2. The tour guide's performance model.

This research has discovered multiple issues. Initially, it was observed that the tourists' enhanced consistent conduct was notably impacted by the tour guide's proficiency. Sustainability training is a crucial subject integrated into the curriculum. Tour guides who have received proper training are capable of accompanying tourists on cultural trips [9]. Several distinct research investigations offer empirical evidence for the importance of tour guides' performance in ensuring tourist satisfaction [35,45,46]. Based on this study, travellers who are content with their tour guides are significantly more likely to express inquiries regarding sustainability concerns. This satisfaction is the result of the tour guide's proficient advisory services at historical heritage sites, where they aid tourists in maintaining the cleanliness of the environment, appreciating the attractiveness of the site, and promoting conservation. This greatly affects the sustainable behaviour of both tourists and caretakers at conservation sites.

Furthermore, the findings confirm that the experiences of visitors significantly influenced the relationship between sustainable behaviour and the performance of tour guides [13,14]. Tour guides assist travellers in their efforts to preserve cultural heritage places. These actions have the potential to mitigate environmental impact, promote the preservation of cultural heritage, and garner support from tourists in relation to environmentally sustainable activities. The fact that tourists visiting Borobudur heed the recommendations of tour guides to recognise the importance of preserving cultural heritage serves as proof of this phenomenon.

Although this research primarily examines the curriculum and training of tour guides, there is always room for improvement, particularly in terms of connecting the field of tourism sciences with other academic subjects.

5. Conclusion and recommendations

The Tour Guide Performance Model at Borobudur is a development concept aimed at revitalising

tourism in cultural destinations by focusing on sustainable development. This model prioritises the

curriculum and training of heritage tour guides. And the recommendation on this, they should be

collaborate with professionals such as cultural experts, historians, and archaeologists. Furthermore,

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1. Provide detailed and actionable recommendations based on the findings.
2. Explain how these recommendations can be implemented and their potential impact.

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on hospitality service requires proficiency with technology, including social media and digital marketing. This will build long-lasting relationships with tourist. By implementing these recommendations, tour guides in Borobudur are expected to improve the quality of their services, create an unforgettable tour experience, and support the sustainability of these cultural heritage destinations.

Acknowledgements

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BUKTI KORESPONDENSI REVISI

TOUR GUIDE PERFORMANCE MODEL IN BOROBUDUR

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ABSTRACT

One of **Rebuilding Tourism for the Future through sustainable Development can be by increasing the tourism human resources**. Tour guides can be included. **In cases where a tour guide appears, tourists might receive an explanation of heritage destinations, especially with regard to appropriate behavior during on heritage exploration. which is why studying tour guides is important because one of tour guides' role is to preserve tourism by conserving cultural assets.** Studies on tour guides include studies that examine the issue of tour guides from the perspectives of role, origin, and structure. This is very important because having a tour guide will make it easier for tourists to get to know the tourist destinations they are visiting. This research will fill in the ecosystem of the tourism industry and also the heritage destination through a tour guide competency development model in Borobudur area. Data collection was carried out through participatory observation and in-depth interviews with six tour guides who are members of the Indonesian Tour Guides Association in the Borobudur area. The data were analyzed using Atlas Ti version 9. The results of this study show that a good curriculum and training will have a good Tour Guide Performance Model In Borobudur area. The curriculum consists of implementing (1) the scope of study, (2) content standards, (3) the teaching process, and (4) the assessment process, while the training includes (1) training needs, (2) types of training, (3) trainers, and (4) evaluation.

Keywords: Tour Guide, Tour Guide Model, Heritage Destination, Rebuilding Tourism

1. Introduction

The rapid development of tourism is accompanied by Rebuilding Tourism for the Future through Sustainable Development by prioritizing the development of various sectors. One of the important sectors in sustainable tourism development is human resource development. This is very influential, since humans are the subject of Sustainable Development as the main activity. One of the actors in facilitating tourist activities in the tourism product chain is the tour guide. Tour guides perform an important function of providing quality information to tourists, which in turn enhances the experience and create a positive impression of the destination. These job opportunities are seen in the tourism chain, ranging from transportation, communication, attractions, rental services, entertainment, and handicraft products or creative economy (Cetin & Yarcana, 2017). Therefore, the development of tourism destinations and products cannot be separated from efforts to create professional human resources, one of which is a trained tour guide (Cetin & Yarcana, 2017). Competent tour guides also influence the quality of the tourist experience (Chan et al., 2015; Rátz, 2017). They are cultural mediators and intermediaries, communicators, responsible leaders, informants, instructors, and advisors who play a direct role in mediating cultural exchanges between tourists and residents (Ababneh, 2018; Alazaizeh et al., 2019; Weiler & Black, 2015).

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a) Abstract

Studies on tour guides are studies that examine the issue of tour guides in terms of role, origin, and structure (E. Cohen, 1985), problems that occur in tourist guide activities (Ap & Wong, 2001), the quality of tour guide services (Teng & Tsaur, 2021), tourist guide management (Hu & Wall, 2013), and tour guide models (Al-Okaily, 2021; Teng & Tsaur, 2021; Walker & Weiler, 2017). The study reveals many dimensions of guided tours that are important for understanding the complexity of a tour guide's work and contributing to the development of the profession. By mastering the competence of a tour guide, they will be able to work professionally.

Tour guides in cultural heritage conservation are very needed. However, there are still few studies that discuss the role of tour guides in cultural heritage conservation. In fact, tour guides in cultural heritage conservation play an important role in **Rebuilding Tourism for the Future through Sustainable Development**, in which tourists come and get an explanation from the tour guide in cultural heritage conservation. It is absolutely essential to ensuring the sustainability of the culture. With the assistance of a tour guide, tourists may comprehend appropriate behavior when in areas of cultural heritage. In addition, this research will fill the ecosystem gap of Rebuilding Tourism for the Future Sustainable Development through a model of developing the competence of tour guides in cultural heritage conservation areas. One of cultural heritage conservation areas is Borobudur. Thus, this research focuses on tour guide performance model in the Borobudur area. This model is based on curriculum and training for tour guide performance.

2. Literature review

2.1. Tour Guide

Working in tourism becomes very important when someone must be able to adapt competencies holistically between the needs and developments of the times. One of the fields of work is that of a tour guide. Mastery of tour guide competence is very necessary in Rebuilding Tourism for the Future through Sustainable Development so that tourists are satisfied and come back to tourist destinations. Tour guides are people who accompany tourists on a tourist trip, so in carrying out their performance, special skills are needed that must be learned and achieved professionally (Cetin & Yarcan, 2017). The tourism industry needs tour guides to support several functions in tourism. These functions include tour guides as communicators and ambassadors (Aloudat, 2017; Teng & Tsaur, 2021), who are able to create good relationships with tourists (Hwang & Lee, 2019) so they must work professionally.

Another function of tour guides is to make tourists revisit them because of memorable experiences, especially when visiting heritage sites (Pine & Gilmore, 1998) where a guided tour of a heritage site has routes and stories recorded about heritage sites (Chelaramani et al., 2017). Effective guiding techniques are able to minimize the negative impact of tourists on heritage destinations by increasing the sustainable behavior of visitors (Rutherford et al., 2015).

The competence of tour guides can be developed through tourism education (Sukrispiyanto & Setiawati, 2020; Yani et al., 2020) through extensive training stages (Yoga et al., 2022) in order to acquire expertise, knowledge, and skills (Weiler & Black, 2015) towards competence. Competent tour guides are able to provide satisfaction for tourists and will make repeat visits (Chan et al., 2015).

2.2. Heritage Tour Guide

Heritage sites have significance as tourist attractions that specialize in cultural awareness (Saha et al., 2017). Involving one of the tourist complexes is a World Heritage Site. Cultural heritage tours have become more interesting to visit as a consequence of their popularity. As a result, there is a growing number of tourists with diverse perspectives and personalities. These diverse qualities and personalities, such as littering, vandalism, and pollution, have the potential to negatively impact the location (Timothy, 2011). However, a tour guide may recognize this, among other things, by keeping track of the route explored (Chelaramani et al., 2017). This significant tour guide's function as a guardian of the values of the natural and

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b) Introduction:

- The authors need to present a clearer gap of why this study is important. Furthermore, this study needs to be linked with the proceedings theme, especially in the field of cultural heritage conservation.
- No need to write the research question in the Introduction section as if it's a student's thesis. Present it as a problem statement that needs to be studied.

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c) Literature Review

- There is a need to present past studies that display the relationship between tour guide competencies and how it significantly helps to the cultural heritage conservation.

cultural heritage is inspiring tourists to adopt sustainable, ethical behavior (Imon, 2013). It's important for the tour guide to advise the tourist on behavior and exploration techniques. Through the development of a sustainable tourist experience, interpretation carried out by a skilled guide becomes a useful strategy to minimize the damaging effect of tourists on heritage materials (Alamineh et al, 2023; Veloso, 2019). However, the competence linked to this significant role's performance still has to be identified. Some tour guides have yet to reach the peak of their expertise, despite the fact that their skills are essential to tours now. Due to the fact that tour guides' performances have a great direct impact on how satisfied tourists feel with their services and a secondary impact on how satisfied they are with the overall tour experience (Al-Okaily, 2021). For this reason, defining the right model of tour guide competency is essential.

2.3. Competency Model

Competence is a concept that is related to a competent work situation (Wilkinson et al., 2010). Competence is a person's underlying characteristic of "how to behave or think, understand the whole situation, and endure for a long enough period of time, enumerating five characteristics of competence, namely (1) motivation, (2) character, (3) concept, (4) science, and (5) skill. This competent character is able to be an indicator of appearance in a person working rationally. Competence relates to the quality of a person at work. Someone who works competently tends to be an excellent achiever (Levenson et 'al., 2006). Competence emerges as a concept of motivation to achieve competence (White, 1959), and to obtain competency functions in accordance with the competence of the field of work and professionalism in work (Amage et 'al., 2014). Competencies will change the way a person works through job responsibilities, with a focus on technical and behavioral performance. With this competency, performance appraisal clearly addresses what is being assessed and how to assess it.

The application of performance appraisal relates to what and how to assess competence. These competencies relate to performance situations, communication skills, and service skills (Gaffard, 2007). In this case, the performance assessed is related to these skills, so in their development there are several competency models. The management-focused competency model is known as the Lancaster Managerial Competency Model as a universal or general management competency framework (Burgoyne & Stuart, 1976). Burgoyne and Stuart group competencies into three main groups, namely (1) the level of basic knowledge and professional knowledge relevant to competency achievement indicators, namely being able to understand knowledge of the field of performance (general knowledge, interdepartmental relations, and objectives of the field of performance); (2) skill level with indicators of competency achievement, namely skilled, resolute, able to withstand emotions, and responsiveness; (3) the level of meta-quality of self with indicators of competency achievement, namely creative, being kind, and always developing themselves. In this model, personal qualities have been contained, but they are still general competencies that must be mastered in the company's management so that they can still be developed specifically for the implementation of the stages.

2.4. Tour Guide Competency Model

The tour guide competency model that has been studied is a sustainable training and transformative model (Walker & Weiler, 2017). This model focuses more on ecotourism guidance with indicators of training, personal qualities, and attitudes towards loving the environment. The competency model of tour guides is also developing according to the needs of the tourism ecosystem. This model focuses on appearance while working (Al-Okaily, 2021). Assessment orientation on tasks, constructive behavior, and counterproductive attitude in tour guides.

Tour guide competency models in developing countries focus more on training tour guides with the aim of increasing sustainable capacity (Weiler & Ham, 2002).

2.4. 1. Curriculum

The curriculum is closely related to how competency are structured and taught to tour guides. Existing competencies are contained in a curriculum. In the education curriculum, there are knowledge, skills, and innovation (Wattanacharoensil, 2014) which the tourism education curriculum has as reference for the development of tourism education (Oktadiana & Chon, 2017). The development of tourism curriculum content in Indonesia consists of skills, knowledge, and attitudes identified by considering their application (Yusuf et al., 2018). The application consists of (1) the scope of the study, (2) content standards, (3) the teaching process and (4) the assessment process. This study specifically addresses the relationship of curriculum with the scope of study related to tour guides as the most essential. Tourism curriculum that contains skills in the field of tourism performance, one of which is to contain tour guide skills as the core curriculum (Tang & Gao, 2012). The tour guide skills curriculum as a core curriculum can provide a reference in the focus of competency development.

2.4.2. Training

Good training is an inseparable part of curriculum. To be able to achieve competence, it is necessary to develop and implement a number of mechanisms, such as training, professional certification and tour guide licenses. Training is a process of knowledge transfer (Freire, 2013). This tour guide competency training can be carried out properly by implementing the references regulated in the curriculum. Training (Wilkinson et al., 2010) is a systematically planned program which contains four stages (1) identification of training needs, (2) types of training, (3) trainers, and (4) follow-up and evaluation. These four stages need to be implemented in order to be able to improve the performance of tour guides. Training in tour guidance can improve the performance of tour guides (Ong et 'al., 2014). Training is necessary so that tour guides are able to work well to achieve competent capacity. Tour guide training will support their competence (Mason & Christie, 2003).

3. Methodology

This study used qualitative methods. Participatory observation and in-depth interviews were used to collect the data. Then an in-depth interview was conducted, and data collection was carried out through participatory observation and in-depth interviews with six tour guides who are members of the Indonesian Tour Guides Association in the Borobudur area. The data were analyzed using Atlas I version 9. Atlas/Ti is an analyze program for analyzing communicated messages (Ronzani et al., 2020). This section is a qualitative analysis that explains the answers to research questions after interviews with informants. The stakeholders' in-depth explanations actions, and observations from the interview were categorized in this research. The analytical resources generated by Atlas.ti™ contribute to scientific research, especially in the social science disciplines (Discussão, 2020; Ronzani et al., 2020).

The analysis step includes several steps, starting with coding by entering curriculum and training data. Then the data is synthesized and analyzed to identify the theories and concepts learned by the researcher. The following sections will discuss each theme in depth in developing the conceptual framework of the Tour Guide Performance Model in Borobudur (Figure 2)

4. Results and Discussions

Borobudur is one of the heritage destinations in Indonesia. Borobudur's temples have been designated as heritage sites, including the Mendut, Borobudur, and Mendut temples. As heritage sites, they must be explored by a tour guide. The research presented in Borobudur

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d) Methods and Analysis:

- Is the description of methods adequate for replication by others (if not a standard method)?

Need to present the justification of using Atlas I version 8.

revealed that tour guides possess a history of proficiency. The phases of comprehending the curriculum tour guide and completing training helped to create this competency. Both of these components create a framework for the model that this study will adopt. And this model can be used to **Rebuild Tourism for the Future through Sustainable Development**, especially heritage destination.

Tour guides are competent to guide and explain to tourists how they should behave at the heritage site by learning the curriculum and having completed training. It is known how tour guides have mastered this procedure when guiding tours. The curriculum that has been put in place is successful in that it helps tour guides comprehend the concept of guiding heritage through coaching from trainers who have expertise in the profession. Tour guides have to complete several types of tests as part of the learning and training process in order to be certified as professional tour guides. After becoming competent, the tour guide will be given a certificate of competence that they can use to get their identity card.

By discovering that training consists of (1) training needs, (2) types of training, (3) trainers, and (4) evaluation, the curriculum consists of the implementation of (1) the scope of study, (2) content standards, (3) the teaching process, and (4) the assessment process. Therefore, tour guides can perform their job effectively by advising tourists to use clothing and sandals (Upanat) while exploring Borobudur Temple in an environmentally conscious manner. Besides that, it restricts the number of tourists who can visit the Borobudur temple and forbids them from climbing the structure, hurling trash in any way, or writing graffiti on its walls. This tour guide's perspective on investment should have an effect on the sustainability of tourism through cultural heritage.

Figure 1 Borobudur Heritage Site

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e) Results and Discussion:

- Is the discussion adequate? Currently no discussion is provided in this section. The authors need to provide discussions of the results and support them with current references. Also, link the discussion to the theme of the conference, that is to preserve cultural heritage. The discussion helps the reader to understand more about the findings of your research.

This link the discussion to the theme of the conference, that is to preserve cultural heritage.

4.1. Curriculum

(1) Scope of Study,

The curriculum implemented has used studies that are integrated with the cultural diversity curriculum so that tour guides can easily understand the material and implement it in work. The curriculum developed has been carried out continuously and planned so that it has novelty that can be adopted by tour guides. This tour guide curriculum development model is an attitude display of curriculum implementation that contains ideas, characters, and processes for mastering interrelated material.

In addition to the curriculum, tour guides in the Borobudur area have implemented the Innovate service Organization and Management Model in serving tourists. This can be seen from the way they transfer information when guiding using thematic methods in the Borobudur Area. This thematic method is able to provide flexibility for tourists to enjoy the tour guide process.

(2) content standards,

The content standard contains references to learning that will be derived from subject matter by providing opportunities and structured freedom for tour guides to improve the mastery of technical competencies (hard skills) and work culture (soft skills) applied at the Borobudur (Heritage destination location). It was found that the curriculum was prepared by competent parties from the association of Indonesian tour guide associations. In addition, in the curriculum there is also an allocation of achievement time in accordance with the tour guide scheme which contains benefits.

(3) The teaching process,

The teaching process includes mastery of knowledge of Borobudur, attitudes to serve tourists, and story -telling techniques using foreign languages. The teaching process includes the technical delivery of presentation material that is easy to understand with modules. This teaching module is distributed according to the material delivered with a good teaching approach and in accordance with the number of tour guides.

(4) assessment process,

The process of assessing the competence of tour guides in Borobudur is a process of evaluating the skills, knowledge, attitudes, and behavior of tour guides in carrying out their duties.

Skill assessment consists of a tour guide competency assessment process to ensure that tour guides have adequate qualifications and can provide a safe, informative, and satisfying travel experience for tourists in Borobudur Heritage Area destinations. The assessment process is carried out through practical examinations in accordance with the material delivered with adequate assessment duration and there is a follow-up of training assessment results (competent or not yet competent)

4.2. Training

(1) Tour Guide Performance Training Needs

Tour guide training in Borobudur as Heritage destinations focuses on the following skills:

- a. **Knowledge Base:** Historical, Cultural Knowledge and Local Insights especially Borobudur as Heritage Destination. Tour Guide have understood well about the history, culture, and philosophy in Borobudur and also able to explain information about history, local culture, local customs and recent developments in the area.
- b. **Quality Service:** as good tour guides, they have to have a good hospitality services and problem-solving skills. They have to know how to handle unexpected situations and solve problems at Borobudur Heritage Destination and also have a customer-centric service mindset, focusing on making the tour enjoyable and memorable for participants.
- c. **Communication Skills:** tour guides have to have a good public speaking, language skills, and interpersonal skills. Tour guide should present performances using effective public

speaking techniques, including voice projection, articulation, and engaging storytelling to international tourists.

- d. **Good Navigation:** tour guide has to create and know the route planning and includes an interesting route, time schedule and total number of tourists handled. It is included in emergency procedures for evacuation procedures and first aid basics for tourists.
- e. **Environmental Awareness: tour guides need to explain** Sustainability by teaching tourists the principles of sustainable and responsible travel by explaining the use of special sandals and special clothing when at Borobudur Heritage Destination.
- f. **Cultural Sensitivity:** training that provides understanding for guides to be sensitive to cultural differences and tourist behavior.

(2) Tour Guides Types of Training,

Training provided for tour guides in Borobudur (heritage destinations) can be in the form of classroom teaching, practice, and learning at work by traveling around the Borobudur area and its surroundings. This practice consists of guiding techniques in the form of introductions, guiding content and closing

(3) Tour Guide Compliance Trainers,

Training provided for tour guides in Borobudur Area is guided by tour guides from the Indonesian Tourist Association, international tour guide practitioners and heritage area tour guides. And this is very good for Rebuilding Tourism for the Future through Sustainable Development especially heritage destinations.

(4) Tour Guide Evaluation

This practice evaluation is in the form of the practice of guiding tours in the Borobudur heritage area with competent or incompetent results organized by the Tour Guide Professional Certification Institute and the Indonesian Tour Guide Association of Central Java.

Based on two things (Curriculum and Training), the results of the Tour Guide Performance Model In Borobudur include:

- a. Resolutiveness and resolve of the conflicts, can be performed when tourists experience difficulties, these tour guides provide the right solution
- b. Problem Solving Skills are the ability of tour guides to identify problems, analyze answers, and implement the best solutions.
- c. Interpersonal Skills are the ability to control themselves, have a high sense of empathy and have a good leadership spirit.
- d. Innovation Skills and able to advance technology are necessary to adapt to technological advances.
- e. Critical Thinking and decision making require being able to think intellectually in a reflective, independent, and rational manner. This includes the ability to provide interpretation, which is informative and argumentative in interpreting and deciding according to observations, information, and argumentation.
- f. Collaboration is the ability to work with tourists and other workers.
- g. Self-Confidence is having high confidence in carrying out duties as a tour guide.
- h. The new ideas and solution is to have ideas for making the guiding atmosphere happy and familiar.
- i. Applying and synthesizing information means that, the Borobudur tour guides have compiled the guide material well so that the tourists are clear and revisit their intention.

Here is the tour guide's performance model

Figure 2

Historical site research is the study of the methods of development, origin, and context of societies as explored through artifacts and architectural structures with the goal of determining historical conclusions. The cultural impact of the history displayed and the understanding received from following the tour could be better understood by tourists with the assistance of a tour guide. The tour guide facilitates this recognition so that tourists are capable of understanding and educate tourists about the cultural heritage that exists in Borobudur. This study was created on the performance of tour guide's demonstrated tour guide competency. This method also acknowledges the vital function that qualified tour guides' skills play in historical sites. The literature review indicates that curriculum and training are important factors in how well tour guides perform in terms of tour guide's competency in Borobudur.

The literature review indicates that curriculum and training both crucial elements on it. The creation of positive relationships between tour guides and tourists can be influenced by the implementation of curriculum and training programs. Positive interactions as these are expected to increase satisfaction among tourists and increase knowledge of heritage sites, therefore will improve promotion through word-of-mouth. It will subsequently investigate the sustainability of the destination by analyzing the behavior of tourists and tour guide's performance at the historical site.

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

The Tour Guide Performance Model In Borobudur is one of the development models for rebuilding tourism for the future through sustainable development especially in heritage destinations. This model focuses on the curriculum and the training for the heritage tour guides. However, existing developments are added to the mastery of technology, especially how to use social media properly and correctly so that it is always connected with tourists who have been guided and tour guides provide good performance for sustainability of the heritage destination.

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) Results and Discussion:

Currently no discussion is provided in this section. The authors need to provide discussions of the results and support them with current references. Also, link the discussion to the theme of the conference, that is to preserve cultural heritage. The discussion helps the reader to understand more about the findings of your research.

This is link the discussion to the theme of the conference, that is to preserve cultural heritage.

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5. References -

- The authors should provide more recent references.

I LAlready give provide more recent references.
Thanks

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6. Length of Paper – Please consider whether the ideas are appropriate for the length. If the paper can be shortened, can you recommend which part(s) to be deleted or shortened?

The manuscript length is **too short (6 pages)**. The authors can add more in-depth discussion and relate it to the cultural heritage conservation.

My Revision : It's 10 pages